

WORKING MEMORY AND LEARNING DIFFICULTIES: COEXISTENCE OR A STRONG RELATIONSHIP?

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Abstract:

This research paper addressed the relationship between Learning Difficulties and Working Memory of a sample of primary students in 10 schools at 4 cities of Cyprus. Students with poor working memory have a low academic achievement, facing difficulties in reading and mathematical thinking. The main objective of the current research is to investigate the possibility of a causative interaction between working memory and the occurrence of learning difficulties in primary school students. Evaluating working memory in students with SLD, the analysis showed that it was significantly lower ($p=,000$), indicating a strong correlation between working memory and learning difficulties. Specifically, the analysis revealed a statistically significant correlation ($p\leq.001$) between working memory and the variables of digit span, picture memory, pattern memory, grapheme discrimination, phoneme discrimination, and phoneme composition. Adding to the research, the current study stress that in students with learning difficulties the deficits in working memory are in a strong relationship

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with difficulties in specific types of both Sequence Working Memory and Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness.

Keywords: working memory, learning difficulties

1. Introduction

1.1 Memory

The term "memory" is commonly used (a) as a mental record of experiences and (b) as a process of recovering these recorded experiences. Both of these definitions have shortcomings (Lieberman, 2012). Memory refers to one's ability of man to encode, store, maintain, and whenever necessary to recall information and experiences of the past recorded in the brain (Boyer & Wertsh, 2009).

A brain whose composition resembles a hierarchically structured network composed of different functional areas (Shepherd, 1997).

Spear & Riccio (1994) gave to the word "memory" the following three definitions:

- 1) the location where the information is kept;
- 2) the area that retains the contents of the experiences;
- 3) the process one uses to learn (acquire), store, or retrieve (remember).

For Gruber (2011), memory refers to processes and systems that are responsible for storing, retrieving and using information when the original source of information is unavailable. Acquiring information, learning and storing it, allows the person to repeat it successfully, avoiding the mistakes in the information he has gained. However, from the past we remember a very small percentage given that only about 1% of our experiences are stored in the long-term memory (Walker et al., 2002).

According to the American psychologist Eudell Tulving (2006), we are the only living beings able to remember episodes of the past and anticipate future events by deliberately planning their actions.

Essentially, there are three main processes of memory: encoding, storage and retrieval (Cherry, 2018).

- encoding: the information enters a person's memory and creates its own trace;
- storage: the information trace is stored in the memory;
- retrieval: the person recalls the trace, re-activates the experience (Dudai, 2002)

The above processes are not necessarily separate stages that occur sequentially, but represent the process of memory (Forde et al., 2012)

Nevertheless, the mechanism of memory remains one of the great and unresolved problems (Lieberman, 2012; Poo et al, 2016) There are times when we cannot re-activate we once remembered. We may forget things that we have experienced and learned but that we have not eventually stored in our minds (Kelly, 2016). According to the theories of interference, of the 1950s and 1960s, people forget events due to the occurrence of other intrusive events (Crowder, 2015). More recent theories, however, "justify" forgetfulness by giving responsibility to the overloading of recovery points, which in fact is an adaptive aspect of memory (Storm, 2011).

1.2 Working Memory

The cognitive mechanism of working memory is present in almost every kind of routine activity and is changing progressively between the ages of 5 to 17 (Alloway & Alloway, 2013). It is independent of the social background of the individual, the economic situation in which he / she is, the educational level of the parents (Alloway et al., 2014), while it is automatically affected by any experience affecting the executive system (Best & Miller, 2010). Nonetheless, it is a basic function for a wide range of cognitive abilities, such as reading or numeracy skills that are highly dependent on working memory (Swanson & Kim, 2007).

Every day we have the need to keep a moment of time in our memory, critical elements, by storing them until we use them. For example, storing a phone number from the moment we hear it until we call it or retention of information to move from one point to our destination or to measuring and use the right quantities of materials (e.g. shuffler 50 gr of butter with 100 grams of flour and add 75 grams of sugar) when we read a recipe but we cannot look at it anymore (Gathercole & Alloway, 2007). All these short-term storages and use functions do well reflect the term of "Working Memory" (Young, 2000). Baddeley (2007) describes working memory as a brain function that retains, handles and processes temporary information required to perform tasks at any time. It is considered by many to be the "workplace" due to its central role in language processing, thought, and action. It has attracted the attention of researchers because of its importance in cognitive function (Romon & Pison, 2011).

Moreover, with the term of "phonological loop" Baddeley (2007) signified the core significance of working memory in the acquisition of grapheme-phoneme correspondence and hence to reading and writing skills (Steinbrink & Klatte, 2008).

Subsequently, many activities that take place in the classroom and require the students to perform a lot of actions at the same time (e.g. listening to the teacher's instructions, while copying proposals from the board), underline the implementation of working memory (Ghani & Gathercole, 2013; Johnson, Perry & Shamir, 2010).

The difference between short-term and long-term memory is that the first keeps information for a few seconds while the second keeps the processed information permanently. The working memory could be said to be an intermediate memory system in the brain that process the information kept for a few seconds (short-term memory) while transferring it to long-term memory (Young, 2000). It is divided into: (a) verbal (or acoustic) working memory, in which words and numbers are transformed into phonemes being stored for a short time, and (b) visual working memory, in which objects images are stored for a longer period of time, capable of processing our minds. (Habeck et al., 2012)

1.3 Learning Difficulties

Memory and learning are two closely related concepts, although not identical (Sumrall et al., 2016). Learning is the acquisition of skills or knowledge, while memory is the expression of knowledge. Differences between them also exist in the speed at which

they occur. According to the American Psychiatric Society, acquiring a skill slowly but deeply is learning. Direct acquisition is memory (APA, 2016).

The same pattern is shared by the view of Gazzaniga and his colleagues, who define learning as the "*process of acquiring new knowledge*" and memory as "*the insistence on learning*" (Gazzaniga et al., 2015).

Lieberman (2012) describes learning as a change in our behavior due to the acquisition of experience. In cognitive - psychological and constructivist models, learning is described as an information processing, which leads to the construction of new knowledge structures with the continuous completion and change of existing structures (Zollneritsch et al., 2012).

According to the United States National Center of Learning Disabilities (2014), Learning Disabilities is a general term that refers to a heterogeneous group of disorders resulting from severe difficulties in learning and using speech, reading, writing, logic thinking, and mathematical competences, while they are focused on dysfunction of the central nervous system (Case – Smith & Obrien, 2014; Pesova et al, 2014; Rose, 2009).

Difficulty in learning can be seen as deficiency or failure of students in school requirements (Weiss, 1992). These issues of inadequacy or failure can be analyzed from a variety of perspectives: learning conditions, socio-political and economic situations, ideologies but also quality of teaching, methodologies, and teacher training (Zakopoulou et al., 2013). However, the student's individual capacity and disposition (Weiss, 1992) cannot be absent from the analysis. The presence of emotional and behavioral disorders makes difficult to diagnose learning difficulties, while students with such characteristics are at high risk of school failure (Hinshaw, 1992).

For Zielinski (1998, p.13), "*learning difficulties are generally referred to when a student's achievements are lower than tolerable deviations from binding, institutional, social, and individual reference standards, or when the attainment (or failure) of standards is linked to weights that lead to undesirable side effects in behavior, experience or development of the trainee's personality*". Adding to this, students with learning difficulties come to the fore as a result of apparent or inappropriate behavior, expression, unclear, mainly emotional or emotional conflicts (Lehmann & Eitmann, 2014).

Dumant (1994) separated the learning problems into two types: learning disabilities found in cognitive development of students and learning difficulties due to other child problems, but also beyond. It should be mentioned here that in many countries the term learning disabilities has been associated with the term learning difficulties (Martins, 2008).

In the UK educational community, the term "learning disability" refers to students who have specific learning difficulties (e.g. dyslexia) and do not experience mental problems. Differently, "*learning difficulties*" are described as "*moderate learning difficulties*", "*severe learning difficulties*" and "*deep learning difficulties*" (Department of Health and Social Care, England, 2010).

Beyond the general name dispute, students with learning difficulties are quite common in schools and range from 12% to 30% of the school population (Westwood, 2014).

Students with learning difficulties are distinguished by general characteristics, such as limited metacognitive skills, organizational difficulties, adaptation and orientation difficulties, and inadequate control (Fletcher, 2012; Anastasiou & Polychronopoulou 2009).

The particular characteristics of students with learning difficulties are:

- Reading deficits are more observable than any other problem in academic performance, while it is estimated that 90% of students with learning difficulties have reading difficulties (Bender, 2008). In particular, the reading readiness problems were defined as the rate of reading (correct words per minute) (Hunt & Marshall, 2006).
- The lack of understanding of what they read and this leads to difficulty in answering questions about the text they have just read (Friend, 2005). Problems with word recognition make difficult for students to understand what this refers to writing difficulties or skip words in writing or even to read words in the wrong order (Gargialo & Kilgo, 2013).
- Deficits in academic attainment in which students with learning difficulties have an unexpectedly slower learning rate. Students with literacy problems also exhibit serious weaknesses in the central strain and in the phonological loop that is evaluated by recalling, for example, digital sequences (Machler & Schuchardt, 2016). However, no weaknesses are necessarily present in the visual-spatial design that is evaluated by the retraction of visual shapes or of motion sequences (Gathercole & Alloway, 2008).

1.4 Working Memory and Learning Difficulties

The poor skills of working memory are relatively common in childhood although students can be supported in their learning needs when they are affected by this problem. The majority of students with deficient working memory experience problems in reading, mathematics and science throughout primary and secondary education (Gathercole, 2014).

But how does a problem in working memory affect learning? Gathercole & Alloway (2007) believe that students with a problem in their working memory experience learning difficulties because they are unable to meet the memory requirements of many structured learning activities, resulting in the re-word of working memory and the loss of critical information needed to complete activities (e.g. Gathercole et al., 2003).

With respect to the relationship between working memory and mathematical abilities, we should take in account that these correlations vary with age and the level of specialist knowledge (Swanson & Saez, 2003). Mathematical deficits are persistent and difficult to compensate over time (Niaz & Logie, 1993).

Researchers have questioned whether working memory being associated with learning difficulties is also related with IQ (Alloway & Gathercole, 2006). Answering to this, research has shown that the peculiarity of correlations between working memory

and success continues, since differences in IQ have been statistically examined in students (Gathercole et al., 2006).

Alloway et al. (2009) suggest that the memory profile differs according to the type of learning difficulties, indicating that students with ADHD are short on behind in visual memory, while previous research has shown that learning difficulties are related to all memory areas (Alloway & Archibald, 2008).

Summarizing, students with deficient working memory capacity face difficulty coping with the multiple demands imposed in the process, such as: writing slow and painful (Lesaux & Siegel, 2003), being aware of phonemes' and words' construction, struggling early (Hoofst et al., 2007) in mathematics and problem solving (D' Amico & Guarnena, 2005). It is also well supported that working memory is a reliable indicator of mathematical difficulties during the first year of formal education (Gersten et al., 2005).

All in all, survey findings show that the best way to break the vicious circle of low-performance students' learning problems is to use methods that improve their working memory during writing and reading, relieving them as much as possible more (Alloway, 2014).

2. Purpose of the Survey

The main objective of the current research is to investigate the existence of a strong interaction between working memory and the occurrence of learning difficulties in primary school students.

3. Methodology

This survey was carried out between January 2018 and June 2018 on a sample of 60 students from 10 elementary schools of cities Nikosia, Larnaka, Limassol and Paphos.

3.1 Participants

The sample was selected by random stratified selection and randomization, resulting in the performance of qualitative and quantitative research (Cohen et al, 2007), consisting of two groups. 30 students diagnosed with SLD (they were attended integration classes) composed the working group (LDG), while 30 students of typical learning composed the control group (CG). The mean age for the LDG group was 96.0 ± 5.8 months (range 88 to 113 months) whereas for the CG 93.3 ± 3.4 (range 87 to 100 months), recording a statistically significant difference (Age LDG vs CG $p=0.044$). Three students in LDG repeated the class. The LDG consisted in 16 boys and 14 girls and the CG 15 boys and 15 girls. The majority of the parents were Greek-Cypriots (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample demographic characteristics

		LDG	CG
Gender	Male/ Female	16/14	15/15
Father	Greek-Cypriot	29	26
	Foreign	1	3
Mother	Greek-Cypriot	28	27
	Foreign	2	3
Father-Occupation	Freelance	15	13
	State employee	6	7
	Private employee	5	10
	Unemployed	4	0
Mother-Occupation	Freelance	3	1
	State employee	4	14
	Private employee	15	13
	Household	8	2

3.2 Tools

Two diagnostic tools were used in the research process: (a) The Working Memory Rating Scale (WMRS), Greek edition (Politimou, Masoura & Kioseoglou, 2015), to measure the working memory of the students and (b) the ATHINA Test, also Greek edition (Paraskevopoulos & Paraskevopoulou, 2011), to determine the occurrence of learning difficulties in specific domains, such as working memory and grapheme-phoneme awareness.

The WMRS is considered to be a commonly applied standardized tool developed on Baddeley's working memory model, with a graded scale of behavior for teachers, targeted to recognize students (5 to 11 years old) with poor working memory (Alloway, Gathercole & Kirkwood, 2008). It completed quickly and results are easily interpreted in four steps: from "no formal" to "very formal". It is a reliable pre-symptom control tool (Andrade & Tannock, 2013) and has been translated into several languages (Politimou, Masoura & Kioseoglou, 2015).

It consists of 20 characteristic descriptions of student with deficits in working memory. The assessment of how characteristic each description is, it is done on a scale of four score points: (0) no typical, (1) sometimes typical, (2) fairly typical, and (3) very typical (Alloway et al., 2009).

It provides an initial, valuable step in detecting potential deficits in working memory. This first recognition can then be estimated in detail with other standardized measurements, such as the Automated Working Memory Assessment (AWMA) (Alloway, 2008).

ATHINA Test (Paraskevopoulos & Paraskevopoulou, 2011) is a test commonly used in Greek for diagnosis of learning difficulties. It is a psychometric scale that evaluates the child's level and development in 14 individual test tasks as well as in five areas of development: mental capacity, direct sequence memory, completion of incomplete representations, grapheme-phoneme's awareness, and neuroscience - psychological maturity.

It benefits from other tests because, although covering the ages of 5 to 9 years old, it can be given to older students who have "severe learning difficulties". At the

same time, it allows the evaluation of all aspects of child development that are considered important for the learning process (Paraskevopoulos et al, 1999).

The general test's statistics define the developmental age, expressed in years and months, showing the amount of maturity of the child and the growth quotient that are integers ranging from 4 to 16 with an average of 10. Similarly, the developmental quotient shows the rhythm, the speed with which the given amount has been won (Paraskevopoulos & Paraskevopoulou, 2011).

4. Statistics

The variables tested were working memory as a dependent variable, while sequence working memory and grapheme-phonemes' awareness were considered independent variables.

Testing the degree of correlation between the above variables, we tried to investigate the following research questions:

- Do students with SLD exhibit deficits in working memory?
- Is working memory correlated with specific tasks of grapheme-phonemes' awareness, such as graphemes' and phonemes' discrimination and phonemes' composition?
- Is working memory correlated with specific tasks of sequence memory, such as numbers, pictures, and schemes memory?

The performance of the participants was assessed correlating the scores in KAEM questionnaire and the scores in specified items of the ATHINA tests. Potential relationship between them was examined using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The significance level was set at 0.05 in all cases and SPSS v22.0 was used for all analyses.

5. Results

Evaluating working memory in students with SLD, the analysis showed that it was significantly lower in LDG ($p = .000$), indicating a strong correlation between working memory and learning difficulties (see Table 2).

Table 2: Statistically significant correlation between working memory and SLD

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.737 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	44.064	2	.000
N of Valid Cases	60		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.50.

It should be noted that we have divided the results of the Working Memory Rating Scale (WMRS) into three categories: The first category included the students with $T < 55$ and normal working memory, in the second category with a rating of $56 < T < 65$ and borderline W.M and in 3rd class with $T \text{ score} > 65$ and abnormal W.M.

We compared the working memory performance between the two groups. Table 3 presents the mean T score for the working memory assessment (KAEM). Percentages in the control group are inversely proportional to those of the working group, as all students showed normal working memory (100%), whereas in the LDG 13% of students displayed normal WM, 47% borderline, and 40% abnormal WM, respectively.

Table 3: Means (SDs) for working memory measures (KAEM) and distribution of students according to the total T score for the two study groups

KAEM	Mean±STDEV	Grade	Normal	Borderline	Abnormal	Total
LDG	61,7±7,4*	B	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1
		C	3 (25%)	6 (50%)	3 (25%)	12
		D	0 (0%)	8 (47%)	9 (53%)	17
			4 (13%)	14 (47%)	12 (40%)	30
CG	46,3±2,7	A	8 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8
		B	16 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	16
		C	6 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6
			30 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	30

Note: Normal: $T \leq 55$, Borderline: 56-64, Abnormal: $T \geq 65$, * $p < 0,05$.

Aiming to test whether working memory is correlated with variables of sequence working memory and phoneme-grapheme's awareness, linear regression analysis was used (Table 4). The students' performance in three subtests (Numbers Memory, Pictures Memory, Shapes Memory) of ATHINA test regarding the domain of Sequence Working Memory and three subtests (Graphemes Discrimination, Phonemes Discrimination, and Phonemes Composition) with regard to the domain of Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness, was correlated with their scores in KAEM. The analysis revealed a statistically significant correlation between Sequence Working Memory and Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness.

Table 4: Linear regression analysis of the relationship between the 6 subtests consisting on the ATHINA test domains "Sequence Working Memory" and "Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness" and KAEM

		95% C.I.			
		B	P	Lower	Upper
Sequence Working Memory	Numbers Memory	-3.126	.000	-4.0	-2.2
	Pictures Memory	-2.635	.000	-3.5	-1.8
	Shapes Memory	-1.817	.000	-2.7	-0.9
Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness	Graphemes Discrimination	-1.835	.001	-2.9	-0.8
	Phonemes Discrimination	-2.459	.000	-3.1	-1.8
	Phonemes Composition	-2.241	.000	-2.9	-1.5

The statistical analysis of students' performance in ATHINA Test and in the tasks of sequence working memory, hardly are changing the conclusions. On the contrary, they reinforce the view that students with specific learning difficulties have severe deficits in Numbers Memory, Pictures Memory, and Shapes Memory (Table 5).

Table 5: Percentiles of Numbers Memory in ATHINA Test

		Group	Percentiles						
			5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	Numbers Memory	WG	1.6500	4.0000	5.0000	6.0000	7.0000	7.9000	9.4500
		CG	7.0000	7.0000	8.0000	9.0000	10.0000	12.0000	13.9000
Tukey's Hinges	Numbers Memory	WG			5.0000	6.0000	7.0000		
		CG			8.0000	9.0000	10.0000		

By looking at Table 5 we see the existence of columns called percentiles. These columns show us the distribution of the variable Numbers Memory. The percentages are determined by dividing the values of the variable from lowest to highest. This helps us find the value of the variable at 5%, 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 90% and 95%. But for better study, we focus on three percent: the 25% known as the first quartile. 50%, the second quartile, which is a measure of the central voltage of the variable, also known as a mean. Basically, it is the average value of the variable when prices are in ascending (or descending) order, as in our case. It is less sensitive to extreme prices and is therefore considered better than average. Finally, 75% is also known as the third quartile.

Observing Table 5, it is realized that 25% of the students working group (LDG) had Development Quotient = 5 and 75% Development Quotient = 7. On the other side, the students in the control group have a Development Quotient = 8 (25%) and Development Quotient = 10 (75%).

In Table 6 we observe that the students of the working group in the 1st quartile (25%), in the 2nd quartile (50% - intermediate) and in the 3rd quartile (75%) have a smaller Developmental Quotient (D.Q) than the control group students.

More analytically:

- In the 1st quartile (25%) the working group in Graphemes Discrimination has a D.Q = 9.75 while the control group has a CA = 12, in Phonemes Discrimination a D.Q = 4 while the control group has a CA = 4. P = 8, and in Phonemes Composition has D.Q = 6.75 while control group PA = 12.

Table 6: Percentiles of Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness in ATHINA Test

Percentiles

		Group	Percentiles						
			5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	Graphemes	W	4.55	8.00	9.75	11.00	13.00	14.00	15.00
	Discrimination	C	11.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	13.25	14.00	14.45
	Phonemes	W	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	8.00	9.90	10.90
	Discrimination	C	6.55	8.00	8.00	10.00	12.00	12.00	13.00
	Phonemes	W	4.00	6.00	6.75	9.00	10.00	10.00	11.90
	Composition	C	6.55	9.20	12.00	12.00	13.00	14.00	15.00
Tukey's Hinges	Graphemes	W			10.00	11.00	13.00		
	Discrimination	C			12.00	12.00	13.00		
	Phonemes	W			4.00	6.00	8.00		
	Discrimination	C			8.00	10.00	12.00		

Phonemes	W			7.00	9.00	10.00		
Composition	C			12.00	12.00	13.00		

- In the 2nd quadrant (50%), the working group in Graphemes Discrimination has a D.Q = 11, in Phonemes Discrimination a D.Q = 6 and in Phonemes Composition has D.Q = 9. The control group in Graphemes Discrimination has a D.Q = 12, in Phonemes Discrimination D.Q = 10, and in Phonemes Composition D.Q = 12.
- In the 3rd quadrant (75%), the working group in Graphemes Discrimination has a D.Q= 13, in Phonemes Discrimination has D.Q = 8, and in Phonemes Composition has a D.Q=10. The control group in Graphemes Discrimination has a D.Q = 13.25, in Phonemes Discrimination has a D.Q = 12, and in Phonemes Composition has a D.Q =13.

At this point it is good to explain that with the term Developmental Cilimus we mean the z - price group's median scale, with an average of 10 and a standard deviation of 3. Knowing the students' developmental quotients, we can decide on three themes of the psycho - pedagogic diagnostic process:

- Percentage of students in the current survey compared to other students
- The diagnostic category for students
- The intra-individual differences between the individual competences and development sectors of students assessed by ATHINA Test (Paraskevopoulos et al., 1999).

In order to make it even clearer, students are those quotients similar 9, 10 or 11 are 50% of the students of the general population and are considered to be in – normal, while students with growth quotient 7 are considered to be marginally low to inadequate, while those with a quotient 8 they are considered marginal low and account for 16% of the general population. In the present study, the students of the working group (LDG) in 50% were under development quotient 8, and respectively, the students of the control group (CG) in 50% were above the development quotient 9.

5. Discussion

It has been shown (Rothlisberger et al., 2012) that working memory, flexibility and self-restraint are considered as important factors for reading, writing and mathematical thinking skills in early-school students.

Working memory plays an important role in the learning process, in the management of instructions inside and outside the classroom (Lamont & Alloway, 2006) and in the creation of visual information (Baddelley, 2006). Students with poor working memory have a low academic achievement (Gathercole et al., 2003), facing difficulties in reading and mathematical thinking (Gathercole et al., 2008). The effectiveness of working memory in learning process has led researchers to find that many learning difficulties have a direct correlation with deficits in working memory (Alloway & Gathercole, 2006), which this study has shown. The students of the working group showed deficits in Sequence Working Memory and, according to ATHINA Test, specific deficits in Numbers Memory, Pictures Memory, and Shapes Memory. At the

same time, they met difficulties in all three subtests of the Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness domain, Graphemes Discrimination, Phonemes Discrimination, and Phonemes Composition, thus confirming that phonological awareness is highly related to reading (Blachman et al., 1994; Saksida et al., 2016).

The low performances in the WMRS and in the tasks of ATHINA test, such as Sequence Working Memory, lead to the conclusion that deficits in memory, in particular in working memory, contribute to the existence of learning difficulties. However, in order to assess the working memory, there been developed weighted tests that accurately and in detail evaluate it (Gathercole & Baddelley, 1996). Such a weighted test is WMRS (Alloway et. al., 2011) used in this research and showed with absolute clarity that the students in the research group had lower scores on the scale with 22 students being in incomplete to poor working memory and only 8 students on a satisfactory scale.

According to Alloway (2006), formal development students differ from one another to the level of working memory. In our research, students in the control group, typical students, seem to have a different level of working memory but all at a normal level ($T < 55$) with a lower $T = 42$ and the highest $T = 53$. The students whose works of working memory are below expected performance then refer to students with deficits in working memory and problems with the '*language learning mechanism*' (Baddelley, Gathercole & Papagno, 1998). Problems, however, are also encountered in the sequence of instructions, copying, mathematics (Hitch & McAutey 1991) and attentive attention (Martinussen & Tannock, 2006).

Adding to the research, the current study stress that in students with learning difficulties the deficits in working memory are in a strong relationship with difficulties in specific types of both Sequence Working Memory and Grapheme-phoneme's Awareness. Specifically, a complicated framework of deficits between numbers, pictures, shapes memory, phonemes' discrimination and composition, and graphemes' discrimination is delineated. Effectively, this framework constitutes working memory and grapheme-phoneme's awareness as a prerequisite for the acquisition of learning process and mostly, of reading and writing skills. As it becomes obvious, the aforementioned finding enhances the argument that working memory weaknesses are related to SLD (Catts, Gillispie, Leonard, Kail, & Miller, 2002; Preßler, Konen, Hasselhorn & Krajewski, 2014).

Consequently, the necessity of early, correct diagnosis as well as effective early intervention (Fuchs et al., 2012; Zakopoulou et al., 2011) is entirely indicated.

The general diagnosis of SLD that the participants were given, without being specified the domain of difficulty (reading, writing, etc.), was one of the main limitations of the current research. Similar diagnoses slow down the more obstacles they create for teachers, as the last do not have a clear picture of the particular difficulties, which some students may meet in specific learning areas. As a result, teachers are not provided with the appropriate tools the use of which could help these students join the classroom, enhance their self-image and empower them as much as they can to cope with these learning difficulties (Sarris et al., 2017).

For a successful participation in a society attached to education, capacity is considered to be a prerequisite. Those who cannot read and write are prevented their access to higher education, thereby reducing their job choices and their financial situation. They exclude themselves from a variety of social and recreational activities (Biewer & Schutz, 2016; Diehl, 2010).

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